

ARE SLING SUPPORTS AN ALTERNATIVE TO SADDLES FOR GRP HORIZONTAL COMPOSITE VESSELS?

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents the strain gauge results from a range of experimental tests on a 2 m diameter, 4 m long GRP liquid storage vessel, supported on Kevlar fabric slings. The results are compared with those previously obtained when the same vessel was supported on twin-saddles, using both steel and rubber interfaces between the vessel and the saddle. Although there is not a dramatic reduction in the strain levels when slings are used some advantages are noted. However, a sling failure when supporting the vessel full of water, clearly calls for a detailed assessment of the sling design to provide a reliable arrangement, for all types of service conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Composite storage vessels are finding increasing popularity in the Chemical Process Industry since they offer a number of distinct advantages over those made with more traditional materials. In those cases where they are used to store hazardous liquids, in the process plant environment, they are generally cheaper to manufacture than their metallic counterpart. This is because when using a conventional metallic vessel a barrier is necessary to protect the vessel to ensure its long-term structural integrity. In the case of carbon steel vessels this is often provided by using a rubber or glass lining. If a glass reinforced plastic (GRP) vessel is employed it is not necessary to provide such a lining, since the resin and glass properties can be selected to tailor their material properties to the process conditions. Having solved the problem of the inner surface barrier, it is also necessary to ensure that the GRP vessel is structurally sound, particular attention being paid to regions of high strain gradient.

Many of these vessels are used in the vertical plane and at zero internal pressure; however, horizontal vessels are used when there is a restriction on height or when there is modest operational pressure. The comparative lightness of these vessels means that they are ideal for storage at elevated heights - such as on an offshore platform. The length/diameter ratio is usually in the range of 1 to 4, although the most common ratio in use is at the lower end of the range, namely at $L/D = 2$. The relatively short length of these vessels means that they could be supported on a pair of longitudinal beams running the full length of the vessels, see ref [1].

However, the more widely used practice is to support the vessel by using a twin-saddle arrangement, located symmetrically some distance from the dished ends of the vessel.

When saddles are employed and the vessel is used for liquid storage, high values of radial interface pressure occur at the uppermost point of the support, known as the saddle horn. These interface forces can be reduced by introducing radial flexibility into the saddle design or by providing a flexible interface, such as a layer of rubber or other low modulus cushioning material, between the vessel and steel fabricated support. This evens out the influence of any surface irregularities, such as high spots on the vessel outer surface and produces a more uniform distribution of the radial pressure.

The avoidance of the 'hard' edge at the saddle horn could be further addressed by designing a structurally more flexible steel saddle, or by introducing a GRP saddle designed with built-in flexibility. Yet a further method is to use a sling or 'soft' support. This latter approach is suggested as an alternative in the Standards, for example in BS 4994 [2], but no details are provided to assess the effectiveness of this type of support over the more conventional saddle support. The aim of this paper is to report the results of recent experimental work where sling supports have been employed. Strain gauge results obtained from these test are compared with earlier results obtained for the same vessel supported on conventional saddles.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The vessel details

One of the experimental vessels, used previously for the study of the behaviour of GRP vessels supported on the saddle supports, see ref [3], was employed in the present investigation of the sling type support. The vessel was of 2000 mm diameter and 4000 mm barrel length. The dished ends were semi-ellipsoidal with an overall height of 500 mm. The lay-up was of three-layered construction; of chopped strand mat (CSM) and filament winding (FW). From the inside surface the lay-up was 2.15 mm CSM, 4.57 mm FW and 4.01 mm CSM; that is, it was non-symmetric with respect to the wall centre. The overall thickness of the vessel was $t = 10.7$ mm. Although this non-symmetry was unexpected and different from the original specification, where a symmetric lay-up was called for, in all other respects the vessel was satisfactory. The vessel did provide an opportunity for examining a non-symmetric lay-up in the test programme, see ref [3]. The vessel was manufactured on a steel mandrel using an automated spray and filament winding system.

Location of the slings and saddle supports.

The supports were located symmetrically with respect to the ends of the vessel. In both cases the centre of the support profile was at a position 750 mm from the end of the parallel length of the vessel. The width of both the saddles and the slings was 200 mm.

Strain gauging and testing procedure

Approximately 160 strain gauges were located on both the inside and outside surfaces in the support centre profile, across and around the support. Particular attention was given to the horn region, in the saddle case, and to the uppermost region, in the sling case, where the sling leaves the vessel. The same testing procedure was adopted for both the saddle and sling type supports. In this the vessel was carefully set up on the appropriate supports, and gradually filled with water at near ambient temperature from a reservoir beneath the test floor. The strain gauge values were recorded at every 10 per cent increment of volume, both during filling and emptying.

At least two tests were carried out for each configuration. The first test provided a 'bedding-down' of the vessel. The values of strain on the second test, which were always within ± 5 per cent of the first, were accepted as authentic and recorded for analysis.

DETAILS OF THE SLING SUPPORT SET UP

The supports for the slings were mounted on the top of existing saddles; see ref [3] for full details. This procedure was adopted for this series of tests, to minimise cost and fabrication time. In an actual situation, where of course the saddle structure would not be available, it would be necessary to design a stand alone structure capable of providing adequate support and restraint. This could be done by constructing a pedestal on either side of the vessel, supported from a base beam.

In this series of tests the intention was to investigate the influence of different sling embracing angles, that is 120° , 140° , 160° and 180° , on the strain levels. The values chosen were the same as the saddle angles used in the earlier work. In order to do this it was necessary to have a means of adjusting the length of the sling. This was achieved by providing a bracket, mounted on the top of the existing saddle, which contained a roller held in position on each side of the bracket by six bolts. To change the embracing angle of the sling, the vessel was lifted clear, the flange bolts released, and withdrawn, the roller rotated to the new position and finally bolted to the bracket support.

To provide a suitable material, from which to manufacture the slings, a number of options were examined. It was noted that sling supports used by some fabricators in Eastern Europe were made of thin sheet steel. This type of sling was considered to lack the flexibility required to accommodate the slight irregularities which occur on the outer surface of the vessel. For this reason it was decided to examine sling material made from fabric. Extensive tensile testing in both the longitudinal and across width directions of the different fabrics was carried out. In the light of this Kevlar 8272 was selected. This was a heavy weave of fabric specially designed for a relatively low elongation to the breaking point. On the basis of the anticipated load to be carried by the slings the factor of safety, based on the failure load, was only 1.8. However, at the design stage this was considered to be adequate, although later experience indicated that a higher safety factor would have been more prudent.

The Kevlar fabric was bonded, using an epoxy resin, at the required curing temperature (60°C), to the knurled surface of the roller over 340° of the roller surface. The sling was then wrapped around the roller approximately twice and the rollers positioned on the top of the existing saddles to ensure that the sling was a tangent to the vessel. The overall arrangement of the vessel in the laboratory is shown in Figure 1, and a schematic arrangement and close up photograph is shown in Figure 2.

Failure of the Kevlar sling.

The vessel was successfully tested and the full pattern of strains recorded for the slings with embracing angles 180° and 160° . However, in the case of the 140° sling, at the point when the vessel was totally full of fluid, at the end of the second load test, one of the slings failed. The failure first started at the edge fibres and spread slowly across the width of the sling. It was not a fast propagation, like a fracture in a brittle material, but took 60 seconds to spread some 25 mm. After the initial failure there was no further signs of distress, the propagation was clearly arrested. The early failure of the sling was unexpected, since the slings had been designed to operate with the 120° sling angle, where the sling load would be greater. Examination of the sling, following

the failure, indicated that the weft fibres (that is, the yarn woven across the width of the fabric) were distorted and as such would not carry the load in a uniform way.

This distortion could have been caused in a variety of ways, such as undue friction at the interface between the vessel and the sling, or a disproportionate amount of the load being taken by one of the outer stitched edges of the sling; these edges were somewhat rigid compared to the main area of the slings. However, since the aim of this paper is to compare the saddle and sling type of support, it is sufficient to say that the present sling material and arrangement did not provide a totally satisfactory method of support. The failure of the sling at this point prevented the tests being extended to consider the 120° sling angle. However, in view of the results obtained from the earlier work it could well be that the use of a smaller sling angle was less appropriate than originally thought.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For the saddle supports

A typical pattern of strain distribution in the immediate horn region, for the saddle supported vessels, is shown in Figure 3a, for the outside surface and in Figure 3b, for the inside surface. The data shown in these figures (indicated by the triangular points) are for the case when the interface was steel (that is, a total absence of any cushioning material at the interface) and the vessel was full of water. The saddle angle was 160°. The full line shown in Fig 3 is that predicted by a theoretical solution for the saddle supported case, ref [3]. The agreement between the experiment results and the theoretical predictions are such that it could well be considered as the 'best line' fit through the experimental points.

In these tests it was noted that a substantial reduction in the maximum strain levels occurred as the saddle angle was increased from 120° to 180°. The use of a rubber interface introduces radial flexibility into the saddle design and a corresponding reduction in strain levels of around 15 per cent. To aid comparison the maximum strain levels for saddle angles 140° to 180° are given in Table 1. The values for the steel and rubber interface are identified.

Angle	Support type	Outside surface				Inside surface			
		Circumferential		Axial		Circumferential		Axial	
		Tens.	Comp.	Tens.	Comp.	Tens.	Comp.	Tens.	Comp.
180°	Sling	1310	-1490	210	-880	810	-1250	580	-310
	Saddle (steel)	600	-1700	475	-700	1130	-600	710	-75
	Saddle (rubber)	660	-1580	680	-410	1150	-710	800	-250
160°	Sling	1145	-1175	1095	-1010	775	-930	570	-375
	Saddle (steel)	900	-2480	750	-770	1500	-910	720	-200
	Saddle (rubber)	840	-2380	720	-610	1650	-910	950	-200
140°	Sling	1390	-1470	1100	-1440	730	-850	780	-370
	Saddle (steel)	1020	-3220	940	-1050	1900	-1150	950	-200
	Saddle (rubber)	1000	-2300	900	-690	1410	-1050	1060	-200

Table 1 Values of maximum strain for Slings and Saddles of 180°, 160° and 140° embracing angles

For the sling supports.

The distribution of the strain on the inner and outer surfaces of the vessel, when supported by the slings, was broadly similar to that of the saddle support, with a number of important differences, two of which are itemised as follows:-

- (a) The circumferential strain at the point where the sling left the vessel (that is at the uppermost of the embracing angle), was found to be virtually zero on the inside surface and of small magnitude on the outside surface. The distribution of these strains is shown on Figures 3a and 3b as the full circles, joined with the chain dotted lines.
- (b) The peak strains, which occur over a relatively short length when the vessel is supported on saddles, do not occur when the vessel is supported by means of slings. The distribution of the circumferential strains for the sling supported case, shown in Figures 3a and 3b, show a more gradual build up to their maximum values than for the saddle support.

Comparison of the maximum strains for the saddle and sling arrangements.

The maximum circumferential and axial strains for both types of support are presented in Table 1 for the three saddle (sling) angles and for the two different saddle interfaces, steel and rubber. Both the tensile and compressive strains on the inside and outside surfaces, are given. The following points are worthy of note.

- (a) On the outside surface the maximum circumferential strain in the tensile direction is of greater magnitude and in the compressive direction of lesser magnitude for the sling case than for the saddles.
- (b) On the inside surface the tensile circumferential strain is always less, while the compressive strain is greater in two cases out of the three, when slings are employed.
- (c) The axial strain on the outside surface in both the tensile and compressive directions, in five cases out of six, is greater for the slings, while for the inside surface the tensile strains are all less and the compressive strains larger.

The only clear fact to emerge from this comparison is that the damaging tensile strains on the inside surface are all less, and the maximum circumferential strains on the outside surface are also less, when slings are employed.

Concluding comments

The experimental work on the slings did not show a dramatic reduction in the overall strain levels in the vessel. Certain strains were reduced and the strain distribution improved to avoid the peak occurring over a relatively small length of vessel. The Kevlar fabric chosen for the sling was not satisfactory; further work is required on the design of this to provide a reliable support.

REFERENCES

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Figure 1 Overall view of test vessel on sling supports.

Figure 2 Arrangement of sling support.

Figure 3 Distribution of circumferential strains; saddle centre profile; water full; 160° supporting angle, for slings and saddle (steel interface).

- ▲ saddle, ● Sling Experiment
- Theoretical line for saddle
- - - - 'Best' fit line for slings